

Parachor and Ring Structure. Part I.

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The parachor's contribution of ring compounds has been investigated by Sugden and his co-workers, and the parachor values of the 3-, 4-, 5-, and 6-membered rings have been determined by them. Sugden in his investigations considered generally the homocyclic carbon compounds with the object of finding the influence of the number of atoms in a ring system on its parachor value. The present investigation is undertaken to decide whether there is any specific influence of a ring structure on the parachor values, or whether the number of atoms (and their mode of linkage) is the only factor to be taken into consideration.

In the present paper, data are given for fifteen cyclic compounds. The surface tension has been determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure. The apparatus employed was of the usual Sugden type. Tubes containing activated charcoal were introduced between the bubbler and the manometer to prevent the fouling of the alcohol surface by the vapour of the liquid in the bubbler, as in the work of Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754). The specific gravity of the liquids were determined with a 10 c. c. specific gravity bottle, while that of the solids by means of a U-shaped pycnometer as employed by Sugden. Pressure differences were read correct to 0.05 mm. and the error is probably not more than ± 0.02 mm. The surface tension and the density determinations were made at the same temperature (± 0.50). The bubblers were standardised with benzene (M.R.), purified by crystallisation and then distillation, and were restandardised before each observation.

The liquids and the solids used were very carefully purified, the former by distillation, generally under reduced pressure and the latter by repeated crystallisation until there is no change in the surface tension or density.

The observed values of the parachor for these substances are given in the fourth column of the following tables; the column headed $\Sigma[P]$ gives the sum of the atomic and structural constants except that for the ring, so that the effect of this structure is obtained by subtracting $\Sigma[P]$ from $[P]_{\text{obs}}$ and is given in the last column.

TABLE I.

Pyridine and condensed benzopyridine rings.

	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	$[P]_{\text{obs.}}$	$\Sigma [P]$.	Diff.theor.	Diff.obs.
Pyridine	25.5°	0.9899	37.52	197.4	191.6	6.1	5.8
Piperidine	27.0°	0.8980	34.87	230.0	224.6	6.1	5.
α -Picoline	26.0°	0.9559	34.74	236.3	230.6	6.1	5.
Quinoline	26.0°	1.098	44.61	303.6	291.4	12.2	12.2
Quinaldine	27.5°	1.053	40.72	343.1	330.3	12.2	12.8
8 Oxyquinoline	98.5°	1.127	39.68	322.8	311.4	12.2	11.4
isoQuinoline	26.8°	1.108	46.28	303.8	291.4	12.2	12.4

It is evident from Table I that the parachor value of the pyridine ring is about the same as that of benzene nucleus. Hence the substitution of a carbon atom in benzene by a nitrogen atom has no effect on the parachor. Moreover, by the fusion of two ring systems as in quinoline and its derivatives, the parachor value of the separate nuclei remains unaltered. This observation is also supported by the work on naphthalene derivatives (Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2017; Bhatnagar and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6,263).

TABLE II.

Five membered ring system.

	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	$[P]_{\text{obs.}}$	$\Sigma [P]$.	Diff.theor.	Diff.obs.
cyclopentanone	29.0°	0.9435	32.33	212.3	204.0	8.5	8.3
Furfuraldehyde	30.0°	1.152	41.09	210.1	202.0	8.5	8.1
Pyrrole	29.0°	0.9309	28.80	166.7	163.6	8.5	3.1
Succinimide	126°	1.242	45.20	206.7	203.6	8.5	3.1
Nicotine	31.2°	1.005	36.50	396.3	382.0	14.6	14.3
Indene	30.5°	1.004	36.99	284.9	272.8	14.6	12.1
Phthalic anhydride	130°	1.238	39.50	295.1	282.8	14.6	12.3
Indole	99.5°	1.070	37.39	270.2	263.4	14.6	6.8

It will be seen that the substitution of a carbon atom in *cyclopentane* derivatives by an oxygen atom has no effect on the parachor contribution; but the replacement by a nitrogen atom as in *pyrrole*, *succinimide* and *indole*, reduces the parachor value by about 5.5 units. In *nicotine*, where the *pyrrole* ring is fully saturated, the normal value is found. It thus appears that not only the nature of the substituents but the degree of unsaturation of atoms in forming a ring as well, influences the parachor to a certain extent. It is also of interest to note that though the condensation of two six membered rings has no effect on the parachor, the condensation of a six and a five membered ring, as in *indene*, *phthalic anhydride* and *indole*, lowers the parachor by about 2.5 units.

It is obvious, therefore, that in this series as in other (*cf.* Sugden and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1868; 1927, 139) the parachor is not strictly an additive function of atomic structural constants, but that these constants vary slightly from substance to substance. The variation in the constant for the five membered ring appears to be in harmony with modern views as to the effects of substituents on the stability of rings. The effect of various other types of ring structures on the parachor contribution is under investigation.

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